

Good single crystal of Cu (terpy) Cl₂ itself could not be grown. So the absorption spectra of polycrystalline Cu (terpy) Cl₂ in the host lattice of Zn (terpy) Cl₂ were recorded in a set up described by Chakraborty and Basu⁶. Spectra of powdered Zn (terpy) Cl₂ (Fig. 1) show band at 22650 cm⁻¹ and 18000 cm⁻¹. Single crystal of Cu (terpy) Cl₂ in the host lattice of Zn (terpy) Cl₂ were then powdered and its recorded spectra show a new band at 14800 cm⁻¹. This new band is due to the copper complex and is in close agreement with the solution spectral data⁷ which shows one absorption band at 680 m μ (14440 cm⁻¹) with E_M = 80.

The crystal spectra of a single crystal of the copper complex in the host lattice of the zinc complex with light polarised along the long and short axis of the crystal (Fig. 2), show two bands at 14500 cm⁻¹ and 14110 cm⁻¹ appearing in both states of polarization while a weak band at 16600 cm⁻¹ occurs only in one state of polarization.

Fig. 2 Absorption spectra of a single crystal of [Zn(terpy)]Cl₂, [Cu(terpy)]Cl₂ in polarised light.

The spectral data, therefore, are in conformity with a distorted trigonal bipyramidal structure for Cu (terpy) Cl₂.

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Determination of Carboxylic Acids Via Formation of Benzylthiuronates.

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CHARACTERIZATION of carboxylic acids as benzylthiuronates¹ is valuable, however, the melting points of many of these salts lie within a narrow range of temperature and the values also depend on the experimental technique employed for the determination. Therefore, it is often desirable that the identification may be confirmed by some independent method. Titrimetric determination of benzylthiuronates with perchloric acid² in anhydrous acetic acid medium using crystal violet indicator affords a useful method for the determination of equivalent weights of the corresponding acids. The water of crystallization present in certain salts can interfere with the determinations. Further, the method suffers from the usual shortcomings of non-aqueous titrimetry. Benzylisothioureia, which is liberated when benzylthiuronates are treated with alkali, undergoes spontaneous decomposition to benzylmercaptan which can be estimated titrimetrically with sodium *o*-hydroxymercuri benzoate³ using thiofluorescein indicator; the procedure, however, has been tested with a few carboxylic acids only. The decomposition of benzylisothioureia to benzyl mercaptan has been found to be quantitative and the iodimetric determination of the latter is an accurate procedure for the determination of equivalent weights of carboxylic acids. The method was tested on benzylthiuronium chloride and benzylthiuronates of carboxylic and sulphonic acids. Unlike the Berger's procedure, the present method is applicable to sulphonic acids as well. The accuracy of the procedure is comparable to that of Berger's. Further, the procedure is convenient as it is devoid of the shortcomings of the non-aqueous procedure. The procedure is particularly valuable in the case of an acid which is not available in the pure form and direct titrimetric determination with a base is not sufficiently accurate. As such, the procedure merits recommendation. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

Determination of Benzylthiuronates.

Benzylthiuronates are prepared according to the reported procedure¹. The salt (75 to 200 mg) is weighed into an iodine flask and dissolved in 20% ethanol. Sodium hydroxide (10 ml, 10% W/V) is introduced and the contents of the flask are swirled for a few minutes. Hydrochloric acid (10 ml, 3N) is then added to acidify the solution. A little more ethanol is added if the solution becomes cloudy. The solution is titrated against 0.05 N iodine using starch indicator.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF BENZYLTHIURONATES

Benzylthiuronium	Calculated	Equivalent Weight	Found*	Deviation (%)**
Chloride	202.63		202.94	+0.15
Oxalate	211.17		211.75	+0.27
Propionate	240.21		239.65	-0.23
n-Butyrate	254.23		253.13	-0.44
Monochloroacetate	260.65		261.45	+0.31
n-Valerate	268.24		268.00	-0.09
Benzoate	288.21		289.10	+0.31
p-Aminobenzoate	303.23		302.14	-0.36
Salicylate	304.21		305.54	+0.44
Cinnamate	314.23		312.75	-0.47
Benzene sulphonate	324.27		322.95	-0.33
p-Toluene sulphonate	338.29		339.42	+0.31
Sulphanilate	339.29		340.35	+0.41
p-Chloro benzene sulphonate	358.72		359.58	+0.24
Naphthalene-1-sulphonate	374.28		373.56	-0.19

* Average of two or three determinations.

** Reported by Berger.

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Studies on Morphine and Related Compounds : Synthesis of 2,5,9-Trimethyl and 2-Ethyl-5,9-Dimethyl-3,4 : 6,7-Dibenzomorphan

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2,5,9-trimethyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan (**5**) and 2-ethyl-5,9-dimethyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan (**6**) were synthesised by condensing 1,3,4-trimethyl quinolinium iodide (**1**) and 1-ethyl-3,4-dimethyl quinolinium iodide (**2**) separately with benzyl magnesium chloride under Freund's reaction conditions¹ followed with subsequent cyclisation of corresponding 1,2-dihydro products (**3**) and (**4**) with 85% H_3PO_4 . The purity of these compounds was ascertained through

titic examination. The structures of **3** and **4** as hydrochlorides, **5** and **6** as bases were established through elemental and spectral studies.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected, spectral studies were done at chemical laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur. Nmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R12B spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard. (Chemical shifts expressed in δ ppm). Microanalyses were done at CDRI, Lucknow.

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